

SMART IOT-BASED AGRICULTURAL GREENHOUSE FARM MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. Farmers' goal is to feed our population and produce high-quality crops so that people can live. Farmers' capacity to grow the food we need is influenced by the consequences of climate change. Climate change is becoming more unpredictable, and more extreme occurrences such as floods and drought, growing seasons, dwindling water supplies, and allowing weeds, pests, and fungus to thrive may all reduce crop yield. The goal of this project is not only to help agriculture in increasing the production of crops but also to implement the Internet-of-Things in agriculture and to provide them a better farming production. The proponents aim to control the water level of the plants, automated devices installed in the project like ultraviolet light and light traps aim to help the growth of the plants faster, and configured set of requirements of different sensors such as the minimum and maximum temperature level, and humidity level. Sensors are controlled and monitored by a mobile application for easy monitoring of farm activities.

Keywords. Greenhouse Farm Management, Internet of Things, Agriculture, Urban Farming

1 Introduction

Farmers grow crops to sell for medical or food use in crop farming. A farmer is responsible for planting, fertilizing, and harvesting crops and must have sufficient and proper knowledge of planting time, harvesting time, and weather patterns to get a good harvest. Some crops are no longer processed and returned to farmers for future use, and seed companies buy other crops to take care of the plant, process it, and resell it to farmers for the next planting season.

The objective of farmers is to feed our population and produce good crops to survive. Our country would slowly die without food; farmers should work hard every day. The effect of climate change influences the ability of farmers to grow the food that we all need. Increasingly unpredictable weather and more severe events such as floods and droughts, growing seasons, and reducing water supply allow the prosperity of weeds, pests, and fungi to decrease crop productivity.

Agriculture is one of the essential facets of a country's economic development, so it is necessary to protect it. Automation in agriculture is needed to increase crop yields while also assisting in the development of the economy. Unfortunately, most farmers in our country practice conventional farming, which involves a time-consuming method of manually examining data related to soil and crops. Modern farming techniques can help to solve this problem. (Naveen, G. et al., 2018)

In the Philippines, urbanization is accelerating, with nearly 49 percent of Filipinos now living in cities, with that number forecast to rise to 77 percent by 2020. Many of the country's major cities, such as Baguio, Cebu, Davao, and Metro Manila, have undergone substantial urbanization. Metro Manila, for example, has a population of over 12 million residents, many of whom live in tightly populated neighborhoods with tall buildings. Congestion, increasing fuel prices, and weak road networks have made shipping farm goods from rural areas to urban markets, where more people and food is eaten, a challenge. (Myler M, et al. 2020)

The importance of agricultural production at constant 2018 prices went down by a negative 3.8 percent in the fourth quarter of 2020. Crops, cattle, poultry, and fisheries both decrease in production. In the latest statistical report, crops which accounted for 57.9% of overall agricultural production, decreased by 0.4 percent. Compared to the last statistics report, crop production increased by 4.8 percent, accounting for 52.7 percent of overall farm production. (Mapa S. 2020)

Different plants need different quantities of fertilizer and water. Too much or too little water or fertilizer regularly would destroy the plant roots, resulting in unhealthy crops. A Smart Plant Management System is introduced to monitor the irrigation and fertilization of plants based on their optimum growth conditions, which include temperature and soil moisture. (Amani Che Rus et al. 2020)

The proponent proposes a project entitled "Smart IoT-Based Agricultural Greenhouse Farm Management" to help the farmers stay connected to the farm anytime and anywhere. Various modules would be used to monitor, control, and collect

information about the field conditions. The farm condition can be configured and viewed by using a mobile application that can be accessed by installing the application and connecting via Bluetooth. The web application can be accessed through the internet. Either desktop or Android phones can monitor the farm. This system can maintain the watering and fertilization of different crops, and fertilization can be scheduled by configuring the time and date using the mobile application. It would result in more production because the crop needs an amount of water and fertilization according to the condition of the soil. This proposed system is also an automated prototype in which the owner can control the farm's temperature and soil condition.

According to the study conducted by Shimoda and Honda (2013), insects are attracted to lights, and yellow-lighting lamps help reduce crop damage caused by nocturnal moths. This prototype aims to reduce the damage by making light traps. According to Bravo, R et al. (2017), the Interactive effects of UV-B light with abiotic factors on plant growth and chemistry and UV-B light help the plants' photosynthesis increase and helps to increase the protection and development of the farm. Ultraviolet light is essential for plant growth. In safe doses, ultraviolet helps plants and crops produce crucial plant oils to improve the flavor and smell of fruit and help them protect themselves from unnecessary UV exposure by acting as their natural sunblock.

2 Review of Related Literature

In economic growth, agriculture plays a vital role for most developing countries. On the other hand, agriculture makes up a lower portion of the national income of developed countries. It has long been involved in the development of essential food crops. Farming is the primary source of income for most citizens and a significant source of income in most parts of the world (Kane Dane, 2020). Agriculture provides a direct source of income for about 70% of the population. Agricultural growth is one of the most valuable resources for ending global poverty, boosting mutual prosperity, and feeding the 9.7 billion people expected to exist by 2050. (IDA, 2020). In this modern world, Internet of Things technologies in agricultural operations reduce manual labor through automation and speed up machinery commands through remote & real-time control. It helps farmers use energy more effectively through regular maintenance and environmental forecasting (Sanchez, 2019).

The evolution of life in all aspects is influenced by agricultural and food security and soil characteristics. The demand for agricultural yield has grown tremendously as the world's population has grown, resulting in large-scale chemical fertilizer production. As a result of this approach of fertilizers and pesticides in farm areas, soil quality, and fertility have degraded. Since expanding farmland with fertile soil is almost impossible, researchers and scientists have focused on developing better and more sustainable agricultural practices (Gouda et al., 2018). Soil contamination is one of the biggest problems of plant growth; over-fertilization and pesticides can affect plants' growth. With this problem, the production of goods would be decreased causing a shortage of vegetable goods in the urban area. The soil could be monitored with this system, and fertilization and Watering are controlled using light traps. It can reduce the insects' damage, and there is no need to use chemical pesticides resulting in good soil conditions.

Methods for reducing water usage and preparing for water supplies are top priorities. The best way to conserve water in irrigated agriculture is to improve water use quality through improved management. Toureiro et al. Validate techniques and methodologies that use remote sensing to assess the amount of water in the soil available at any given time, allowing for the precise implementation of the water depth required to optimize crop development (Toureiro et al., 2017). Watering can affect the growth of crops. With this system, irrigation could be monitored, and maintain the exact amount of water needed for each crop.

Light exposure is the most critical factor impacting plant development, controlling how much light the plants get. Photosynthesis, a plant mechanism that converts sunlight into chemical energy, is driven by light. (Prof Gert Venter, 2017) Active photosynthetic radiation is vital in many plant species. Escobar et al. discovered that UV-B light enhances net plant photosynthesis. Higher flavonoid synthesis can be induced by UV-B and high PAR in young and old plant leaves. When plants are exposed to UV-B, UV-A radiation has a beneficial effect on photosynthesis.

Water quality is essential in deciding the success of nursery and greenhouse crop production, and it should be included in fertilization and disease management (BOSER, 2016). Since farmers usually irrigate crops based on their knowledge, precision agricultural greenhouse systems reveal significant potential for improving irrigation management practices.

Soil-based greenhouse crop irrigation typically calculates daily estimation, while soil-based systems require an hourly or even shorter estimation (Nikolaou et al., 2019). Crops need water to fulfill their evapotranspiration rate to survive their water requirement. The amount of water lost to the atmosphere through the plant's leaves and the soil surface is the evapotranspiration rate (Smart Fertilizer, 2020). The greenhouse requirement for soil base crop production was addressed in this chapter. It also covered greenhouse environmental regulation and management of temperature, humidity, lighting, and nutrients using creative technologies and the equipment needed for an effective production system (Idris Muhammad et al., 2021). Crop water and soil requirements are required for this study; each crop greenhouse needs a different amount of water; by monitoring the soil condition of the crops, this system can maintain and control the irrigation and fertilization of each crop.

The Department of Agriculture (DA) has launched the country's first Smart Greenhouse Philippines Project (SGPP), which aims to boost productivity and grow high-quality tomatoes by incorporating advanced Korean farming technology (DA-AFID, 2019). In this modern world, IoT makes our lives easier, and urban farming needs this kind of system to improve the efficiency of producing crops. Agriculture needs interdependent networks that provide water and energy services.

Climate change and rising resource demands are expected to put these networks under stress. Systems that provide the energy and water resources required for a sustainable food supply enable modern agricultural production. The food-energy-water triangle is formed by this interdependence (Berardy & Chester, 2017). The Internet of Things increases the Efficiency of agricultural and farming processes to boost yields and cost-effectiveness (IoT). IoT, in particular, can improve the efficiency of agricultural and agricultural operations by reducing human interference through automation. (Madushanki et al., 2019). IoT in urban farming is a significant benefit in agriculture because it offers productivity and good crop production. With this method, farmworkers can feel less burdened because of day-to-day farm surveillance. Farmworkers or farm owners may conveniently track and control the farm anytime and anywhere with a mobile device.

Crop production and drought forecasts are essential to farmers and agricultural Farmers may use the dashboard or a personalized smartphone application to get reliable soil data. Executives would benefit agricultural production in countries all over the world. Drought prediction is vital for early warning and minimizes drought risk on crop production. Drought prediction research seeks to increase our understanding of the physical mechanisms of deficiency and improve predictability skills by using all predictability sources (Rezk et al., 2021) due to insufficient and irregular rainfall, decreasing fodder supplies from crop residues. This limits the farming sector's potential further, resulting in lower crop yield in the following farming season. This system aims to predict the weather and climate change to monitor and maintain the soil condition of crops. Smart Farming and predictive analytics Crop prediction is essential because it aids the farmer in making potential decisions about crop production, storage, marketing strategies, and risk management. Networks are used to forecast crop production rates using data obtained from farm sensors.

Smart farming uses modern technologies and related concepts to maximize productivity and economic returns while reducing environmental effects. Farm management information systems (FMISs), which automate data acquisition and processing, tracking, planning, decision-making, logging, and managing farm operations, are among the most critical aspects of intelligent farming (Köksal & Tekinerdogan, 2019).

This project is primarily focused on improving current agricultural practices by applying new technology to increase yield. This research presents a model of an intelligent greenhouse that enables farmers to carry out farm work automatically without the need for extensive manual inspection (Kodali et al., 2017).

In intelligent agriculture, the Internet of Things (IoT) is essential. Since IoT sensors can provide information about their agriculture fields, smart farming is a new idea. The paper aims to use emerging technology, such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and smart agriculture with automation. The most crucial factor in increasing the yield of efficient crops is keeping track of environmental factors (Prathibha et al., 2017). IoT is an essential technology in smart farming because it ensures data flow between sensors and other devices, allowing for automated processing, analysis, and access to the data collected, resulting in more timely and cost-effective development and management efforts on farms.

3 Project Design and Methodology

Smart IoT-Based Agricultural Greenhouse Farm Management consists of an open-source electronic platform, temperature sensor, humidity sensor, exhaust fan, relay module, water pump, ultraviolet light, light traps, soil moisture sensor, and web and mobile application. The open-source electronic platform is the system core or the central processor, and it can be programmed with Arduino (IDE). The internet would act as the user's connectivity, the farm data would be sent online, and using a web application, the farm owner can monitor the farm field. The mobile application can be accessed via Bluetooth to configure the farm operation.

Figure 1. Operational Framework for the Proposed Project

4 Results and Discussion

As shown in Figure 2 is a diagram of the microcontroller and module's possible connections. A website wireframe, often called a page schematic or screen blueprint is a visual representation of a website's skeletal framework. The name "wireframe" comes from other domains where a skeletal structure depicts 3D shape and volume.

Figure 2 shows the layout of IoT-Based Agricultural Greenhouse Farm Management; this wireframe includes connected sensors and devices utilizing the open-source electronic platform, the Esp32 Devkit, as the microcontroller and functioning as the system's brain. The modules and sensors utilized in this project are a soil moisture sensor, a humidity sensor, and a temperature sensor. The proponents decided to add a mobile application and web monitoring to manage and manipulate the system's data easily. The mobile application is linked to a Bluetooth module that is only active when the user is inside the greenhouse and has a length of 100 meters. If the user has a mobile application, the user can use the system. Proponents create Web applications for monitoring to help crop farmers monitor the daily environmental conditions inside the greenhouse due to different and uncontrollable reasons and factors that lead the plants to succumb to disease and die. All gathered data from the sensors be transferred to the mobile application via Bluetooth and Internet connection; if the Internet connection is unavailable or out of coverage, a Bluetooth connection can deliver all gathered data and information to the mobile application.

Figure 2. Schematic Diagram of Smart IoT-Based Agricultural Management

The establishment of the system is a critical step in the project's development. The previous phases gathered and analyzed a solid system foundation. Hardware, software, and a web application must all be constructed to complete the development phase. All sensors and modules were first connected using jumper wires that led to a breadboard and others related to Arduino pins. The proponents started coding and programming the project's fundamental objective and designing a web application for the Smart IoT-Based Agricultural Greenhouse Farm Management system that would be used during this phase.

ESP32 board is the main heart of the project. It provides enough processing power and memory to run the projects, and it can read multiple modules and sensors simultaneously. This allows the ESP32 to function as a stand-alone system or a slave device to a host MCU, lowering the main application CPU's communication stack overhead. Through its SPI interface, the ESP32 can give Wi-Fi and Bluetooth capability to other systems. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. Actual ESP32 and Module Wiring Connections

DHT11 is connected to the ESP32 in PIN 13; The DHT11 is an essential digital temperature and humidity sensor with a low-price label that uses a capacitive humidity sensor and a temperature sensor to detect the air around it and provides a digital signal to the data pin. DHT11 contains two functions of the sensor. First is the temperature sensor. It can detect the temperature environment within the greenhouse farm. The other is the humidity sensor. It can detect the humidity level of the environment in the greenhouse farm. These two function sensors join in 1 device, which is the DHT11. (Figure 4)

Figure 4. Testing of DHT11 in the Greenhouse Prototype

Soil moisture is used to determine the volumetric water content of the soil. It can detect whether the soil condition is dry or wet. The average minimum soil condition water level depends on the soil type. Only the farm owners or farm employees can set the minimum and maximum requirements for the soil's water level. The soil moisture sensor is connected to ESP32 in pin/analog 36. (Figure 5)

Figure 5. Testing of Soil Moisture in the Greenhouse Prototype

The devices of the prototype are the exhaust fan, ultraviolet light, light traps, and water pump; these devices are connected to the relay module, and the relay module is connected to esp32 in pins 18, 19, 21, and 27; the relay module is an electrically controlled switch that may be switched on or off, allowing or preventing current flow. The relay module serves as the switch on and off of the devices installed in the prototype. Each machine needed an input of voltage power, the water pump required 5 – 9 voltages, and the light traps, ultraviolet, and exhaust pump needed 12 voltages of power (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Testing of Relay Module Switching the Devices

Coding the mobile application is used blocks. The proponents studied the Thinkable and how it works by watching tutorial videos on YouTube and reading in forums, etc., to gather information in implementing the instruction for the project. To connect the mobile application to the ESP32 to get and send data, proponents program the mobile application Bluetooth

connection using blocks shown in Figure 7, each block containing a default command depending on the condition of the block codes.

```
when Scan_Picker BeforePicking
do set Scan_Picker Elements to BluetoothClient1 . AddressesAndNames

when Scan_Picker AfterPicking
do set Label30 Text to Connect Your Device

when Connect_BTN Click
do set Scan_Picker Selection to call BluetoothClient1 Connect
address Scan_Picker . Selection
set Label30 Text to Connected
set Login Visible to false
set MainMenu2 Visible to true
```

Figure 7. Blocks Coding for Bluetooth Configuration

A project should be tested on both hardware and software. Before implementing the project, proponents ran a full system test that should be aware of what bugs and errors need to be addressed for the system to run smoothly. Throughout the trial, the proponents of the project experienced several errors, but they can correct them to secure the success of the project, some hardware errors include device and sensor wirings, and in software, the placement of codes is disorganized; (Figure 8) proponents immediately correct these errors, and many testing occurs during this stage to finish the prototype with few errors.

Figure 8. Checking the Wiring and Pins of the Modules and Sensors

Figure 9 shows the actual model of the prototype in which modules, sensors, wirings, and devices are installed. The back of the prototype where the wirings, modules, and mainboard are installed is placed in a rectangular plastic case. All sides of the prototype installed devices like an exhaust fan and host for the water pump. The inside of the prototype is where the light traps, ultraviolet, and sensors are installed.

Figure 9. Actual Model of Mini Greenhouse Incubator

In this stage, the proponents have already finished the project; after the numerous trials and errors are resolved, the project's proponents begin implementation. The proponents went to Puregreen Eco Farm in Brgy. Malabago, Calasiao, Pangasinan, and Tadena Hydroponics Greenhouse by Greengold farm at Osmeña St. Malasiqui, Pangasinan, where the greenhouse farming is located to present the simulation of the project.

Figure 10. Proponents Presenting the Project to the Respondents at Puregreen Eco Farm at Calasiao

Proponents presented the project to Mr. Ramon Reyna, farm owner of Tadena Hydroponics Greenhouse at Malasiqui. Proponents presented the features and how the project works, such as; easy monitoring of temperature level, humidity level, and soil moisture level of the farm using the web application and easy to manage the farm using the mobile application by configuring the minimum and maximum requirements of each crop.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The proponents conclude that many factors can affect plant growth; temperature, humidity, soil moisture, light traps, and ultraviolet light. Managing the temperature and humidity can help the farm to have a good environment, monitoring the soil moisture level can control the exact amount of water needed for each crop, controlling the pest damage can be lessened using the light traps, and increasing the photosynthesis using the ultraviolet can help the fast growth of the crops.

Based on the conducted survey result, the two farm owners were satisfied with 93 %, and ten employees were satisfied with 95% after testing and using the project, they agreed that using the project can help the farm in terms of automatic fertilization, light traps, and ultraviolet light based on the configured scheduled by the user, give an exact amount of watering based on the soil condition of the crops, easy use of web application and works properly when connecting to the internet for monitoring the temperature level, humidity level and soil moisture level of the farm, user-friendly mobile application, works properly when connecting to Bluetooth and can manage the farm easily.

The project was developed to be applied in greenhouse farming. The proponents recommend the implementation of the Smart IoT-Based Agricultural Greenhouse Farm Management on their greenhouse farm. On the other hand, to avoid untoward circumstances, all current and high-quality IT equipment must be used. The farm owner who monitors the farm should have a personal computer to access the web application, while the farm employee, farm operator, and farm manager who will configure and manage the farm should have a smartphone to access the mobile application. The proponents' recommendation is not only to improve the project but also to broaden the content of the project for future academics who might conduct research on the same issue or related to this project as the proponents, such as using more accurate modules and sensors, such as relay module, temperature, and humidity sensors, which are sensitive, and prone to failure. In the future, proponents should consider more significant technologies that will be useful in today's generation and design an enclosure that will allow all modules to be preserved and available for long-term use.

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